

A case study of Srinivas Hospital Mukka on infectious Waste Management

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ABSTRACT

Waste is a society's inevitable product. The need for environment and livestock is also to handle this waste more efficiently and scientifically. Normally the waste generated at hospital is regarded as Bio Medical Waste. Bio Medical Waste is the type of waste consisting infectious materials. Treatments related to health can generate several hazardous waste forms. For the healthy environment, the careful management of such waste is essential. The most crucial part in the hospital is bio medical waste management, since mismanagement not only affects the environment, but also the human being especially health centre workers. By biomedical waste management rules 2016, the safe disposal of biological waste in hospitals and medical centres is made obligatory. This case study summarises the main issues faced in hospital regarding waste management and various management and segregation practices being followed by the Srinivas hospitals Mukka of Mangalore region.

Key words: Segregation, Bio medical waste, Hazardous waste

Introduction

All human activity produces a sort of waste that can be classified as municipal waste, industrial waste, sewage, agricultural waste and hospital waste. The waste may contaminate water, soil, air and it should be treated with care. Hospital waste is a form of infectious and non-infectious waste that has an environmental and health risk impact. Therefore special planning and management is required, due to the potential hazards of them.

According to Biomedical Waste Management Rules 2016 biomedical waste may be defined as “any waste that is generated during the diagnosis, treatment or immunization creatures in the health care institutions or outdoor”

Hospital waste is usually divided into two types: Non-infectious waste and infected waste. The waste management process is entirely different for each type. Non-infectious waste can be disposed of with normal waste, but in particular infectious waste should be disposed. Recently the number of hospitals has increased rapidly to serve the people. Patients are diagnosed in hospitals and medical centres, but they can also be sites for the transmission of disease. (Borg 2007). Bio medical waste must be properly managed and disposed off to protect environment and creatures. In hospital waste, patients and staff dealing with these wastes are at risk. Infectious and hazardous medical waste. It poses a serious health threat and requires specific treatment and management before final disposal (Hassan, shafiul and anisur 2008). Especially health care workers who are at highly risk of exposure to biomedical waste include generation, accumulation, handling, storage, treatment, transport and disposal. Waste should be disposed of and should not be ignored (Technical guidelines on environmental sound management of bio chemical and healthcare and health care waste 2000). A study of the different processes of waste management and disposal in the various countries. Waste has been found to have a substantial health and environmental impact. Waste management safety measures, waste disposal and laboratory review for infectious waste are insufficient and the knowledge and understanding of medical waste needs to be strengthened. (Nasima akter 2000).

Depending on the nature and risks of generating waste and causing injury during collection, processing and disposal, the World Health Organisation divided biomedical waste into eight different categories (WHO 1999). These include waste, infectious, toxic, industrial, hazardous products, sharps, pharmaceutical and pressurized containers. In the various types of waste, greater attention and precautions are needed during handling. These may include sharps (needles, scalpel blades etc.), Microbiological and toxic contamination (blood samples, body tissues organs, microbiological cultures etc.) and other infectious wastes (contaminated syringes, catheters, IV set, etc.). In addition, other environmentally sensitive by-products such as radioactive waste, mercury devices and plastic materials (syringes, bottles, packaging material etc.) are the other kind of wastes generated in the health care

institutions. (ashakiran et al 2004) Biomedical waste management provides the health and safety of health workers and citizens with proper hygiene. (Almuneef M et al 2003)

Research objectives

- To identify the status of the hospital waste management
- To examine the hospitals waste management process in the Srinivas hospital.
- To identify the factors affecting the management of infectious waste.

Case methods

Exhaustive literature review regarding the concept and theories has been done through collecting latest Journals from Google Scholar. Secondary data has been collected from various like books, journals, report of the hospital , websites of hospital , magazine, newspapers and unstructured interviews undertaken with bio medical waste management committee head of the hospital.

History of Srinivas Hospital

In 2009, A Sharma Rao Foundation launched Srinivas hospital with a vision to transform society through education by establishing academic institutions in a complex balance and its social, ecological and economic environment that continually strives for excellence in education, research and technical services to the country. The medical college and hospital located in Mukka, Mangalore, India. Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre is affiliated to RGUHS and is recognised by the council of India.

Waste segregation, collection and storage

By the Biomedical waste management rules 2016, the segregation into a different color coded bag of bio-medical waste helps to understand the distinction and the effective disposal of bio-chemical wastes. Segregation is a major step in the management of waste as segregation errors endanger those who control waste further in the waste management chain. (Taylor 1988).

Green bins were made for general waste: waste from the kitchen, food, clothing, water and bottles. Infected plastic bins composed of: siring, gloves and hazardous waste which disposed in Red bins. Infected waste in a yellow bin: soiled, anatomic, chemical substance, cytotoxic, waste from labs, expired and destroyed drugs, body parts. Glassware: glassware, metal plates,

antibiotic vials and White cups: needles and broken glasses consisted in Blue bins. These are some commonly used color codes in the hospitals, but some private hospitals slightly vary their color codes according to their convince and availability.

Types of biomedical wastes in Srinivas hospital

The different types of waste generated during the routine treatment and teaching practices of the institution was categorised as per the schedule described according the Biomedical Waste Handling and Management Rules 2016. The waste categories included: general, surgical waste, kitchen waste, disinfected waste, sharps. The general wastes were found in all departments in different forms and were segregated in black bins. Sharp wastes were segregated in PPC container in all departments. BMW's hospital management system shows that relatively large amounts in health care and indiscriminate disposal of BMW are created on a daily basis, and that exposure to BMW poses a serious risk to environmental and health conditions requires specific treatment and management before disposal is completed. (Praveen mathur et al 2012).

Management of general wastes

General waste from the hospital consists of: organic waste-mostly food remains and kitchen related by-products, paper waste, plastic waste, bottles. Each department from the Srinivas hospital generates general waste which is mostly gathered in a black bin with disposal black cover and when the bin is full or at the end of the each day the housekeeping personnel in charge collects the waste to be put in black polythene bags. Ramky environmental engineers unit of Mangalore collects this waste and carries this to the centralised waste treatment plant on daily basis. A experiment was performed on two batch types of medical waste incinerators, one with a mechanical grid and the other with a solid grid for disposal of general and limited medical waste. (lee et al 2000).

Management of solid and chemical waste in yellow bins

The waste which includes human body parts, human tissues, placenta, chemical waste, liquid wastes are being collected in the yellow coloured bins and transported to the central collection unit. The central collection unit transports this waste further to the incinerator. A analysis of bacteriological profiles for BMW with the review of procedures in management and disposal with standard procedure was done in Sharada hospital at greater noida. (Vichal Rastogiet al 2011).

Management of sharps and glassware

As per revised guidelines the sharps which include metals, needles, fix needle syringes, scalpels, blades etc., are collected in PPC containers. These are puncture proof and leak proof. These containers are transported to central collection unit for further treatment and transport to incinerator. The other sharps like glassware, broken or discarded glass and metallic implants are collected in red coloured bin. These are then further transported to the central collection unit.

Management of plastic material

Srinivas hospital uses blue coloured plastic bins for the collection of recyclable plastic materials, vials, bottles, syringes, vacutainers etc. The plastic material after collection is sent to the central processing unit for autoclaving and shredding. After this the material is transported to the incinerator for final disposal.

Transportation of waste containers

The hospital has provided wheeled trolleys and carts for transporting wastes within the hospital. But only few trolleys are available and most of the containers are transported manually by the workers to the central collection unit of the institution.

Awareness about the Biomedical Waste Management Rules 2016

Bio- Medical Waste Management Rules 2016 which has come into practice in the institution since 2016. After this act the hospital has started segregating the hospital waste in a very systematic and scientific way so that the environmental hazardous and human infectious can be avoided. Only by learning to generate more goods and services with fewer resources worldwide, and less environmental contamination and waste in society and industry in general, will sustainable development be achieved (Waite et al, 1995)

Use of protective and safety measures while handling biomedical waste

Bio medical waste in the hospital are disposed and carried to central collection unit by the lower level worker. The hospital made some safety measures to handle it .i.e. compulsory wearing of gloves, mask, and apron by the workers. And compulsory hand washing after disposed to collection centre. If appropriately handled, all types of incinerators eliminate waste pathogens and reduce waste to ashes. Certain types of waste, pharmaceutical or clinical waste, however, require higher temperatures in order to complete destruction. (pruss et al 1999). During the last two years, Danish municipal and hospital solid waste incinerators have

carried out a comprehensive series of dioxin measures. The study was conducted in Denmark to determine the total annual MSWI dioxin, now estimated to be kg of dioxins and furans. (Manscher et al 1990).

Discussions

In the case of negligence by certain waste administrators or division, it is difficult that Srinivas Hospital collects consolidated waste from different departments. Although there are color-coded waste bins available in different offices, some waste handlers mix the waste too. The fact that certain staff members had not been educated in safe waste handling or ignored management practices was either the result of a lack of sensibility. As a priority for waste collection, black bins are more collected than blue bins as the priority, and depending upon the number of patients in the hospital rely on other wastes. In the article on hospital waste: the environmental hazards and their environment are studied for reference to hospital waste, waste classification and the indicated 1.5 kg of waste is produced per day. The report also highlights the importance of safety measures and the training of waste management staff⁷.

(Hem Chandra 1999). The TQM strategy to control and handle medical waste in the main hospital is addressed in conjunction with the government of India Regulations for the control and disposal of organic waste 1998. A working group consisting of members of physicians, nurses, administrative staff, and housing to address the issue via the TQM was formed in September 1999. (Das et al 2010).

Plastic bins are used in the public domain for general wastes, even though patients drop things such as diapers after changing their kids at times. Most departments in the hospital observe the color coding method, but few people often fail to apply color codes. Mixing waste remains a big challenge and the central waste collection unit collects mixed waste which is not sorted and therefore raises waste management costs. Even though the hospital has put in place different policies on health safety and biomedical waste management the percentage that represent the population that is not aware of the procedures due to lack of training or ignorance is high. An interventional research examined whether the training of health managers on bio-medical waste management awareness has a major effect on the level of health (Aclan Ozder et al 2013).

The training programs in biomedical waste management, mandatory staff training and training courses and strict supervision of current practices for different levels of healthcare

workers are stated. Healthcare professionals must concentrate on training programs on the management of biomedical waste, which are sufficiently broad and realistic in their capabilities. It is important to measure and quantify the amount of medical waste generated in each unit of the hospital periodically to ascertain which unit or department generates the highest and lowest amount of wastes. This may guide the resource allocation process of biomedical waste management.

A written biomedical waste management program must be included in a health care facility's policy and procedure manuals. It must also be included in the facility's in-house education, occupational health and safety measures, and orientation programs for all health care staffs. This program must be regularly reviewed and updated by an appropriate review committee, which includes waste handlers as important stakeholders. Certain basic elements must be embodied in any biomedical waste management program to ensure that biomedical waste is handled and disposed safely and efficiently. Health care facilities must prepare contingency plans for dealing the issues like storage and disposal biomedical waste, excess waste. The effectiveness of waste disposal policies and procedures should be assessed regularly. The assessment process should be described in the policy and procedure manuals and should reflect the quality assurance requirements used in other areas of facility management. Waste should be collected daily (or as frequently as required) and transported to the central designated assembling point. Bags should be specified according to generation of the waste. The bags or containers should be replaced immediately with new ones of the same type. A supply of fresh collection bags or containers should be readily available at all the locations of waste production.

The program scope must be adjusted to suit the facilities and the total waste produced in addition to become functional. The contents of the waste management plan of the hospital must be fully understood by staff, including the rules that apply, how the waste generates can be separated and how environmental material can be chosen and the infectious and hazardous waste can be disposed of properly. A feedback system should also be in place to steer, evaluate and fix deficiencies and issues in a waste management.

Conclusion

The Srinivas hospital is following the bio medical guidelines for the segregation of different kinds of waste. The safety bio medical measures must be effectively implemented in each

hospital as to free from infectious and also for the healthy waste disposal. The proper waste disposal in the hospitals leads to accomplishment of central Government scheme of SWACCH BHARATH.

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